

IMPROVING WRITING ABILITY THROUGH OUR FIVE SENSES

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays English language has become a dominant language on communication among different nations in all areas. People try to find proficient and facile way both in teaching and studying the English language. This article deals with the issues on methodology in teaching writing comprehension through learners of English as a second language. With the help of this work we will be aware of one more way in enhancing writing skills. The five senses technique suit for all pupils inspite of their age and ability.

Keywords. Method, five sense, descriptive, writing ability, visualizing, imagination, sight, sound, smell, touch, taste.

In Uzbekistan, social, economic and cultural differences within the population are associated with great disparities in English proficiency among pupils in elementary schools. As a result, some teachers face on two large group in their classes, where one third of the pupils have never studied English, while another third may already have read The Little Prince. This situation requires a way to plan and different methods in the curriculum to reflect the reality that learners dissent in various ways. When teachers approach differentiate technique, they consciously make the lesson accessible to all pupils, regardless of gender, ethnicity, language or different abilities. [1].

One technique for differentiated class that I employ in my class is the strategy to improve writing comprehension known as 'Writing with all five senses'. It is a brilliant rule for working on description, writing comprehension and increasing the vocabulary. Sight, sound, smell, touch and taste are five simple details that help make pupils' fictional world come to life.

The Five Senses types

Sight. Visual description is the most commonly used of the five senses in writing. Most pupil rely heavily on that what they see, they use visuals to orientate to distinguish

between objects and to understand the world. Therefore, its important to give a strong visual image.

Sound. Sound increase the depth and meaning to a scene. Pupils are to remember whatever their characters are hearing, the readers should hear to. They can also add about volume and duration of the sound in writing.

Smell. Smell is linked strongly to memory and nostalgia. This is because when our brain processes scent, it travels through our memory and emotion sections. If pupils have a new or unfamiliar smell, let them use similes or focus on the emotion the smell activates.

Touch. Even if do not realize it we are always touching something. Clothes. A keyboard. The pages of a book. Touch is a complicated sense. When writing about touch, the physical is very important to describe, but even more important is in the invisible.[2]

Taste. Food is important feature of every culture. When describing taste, touch is another sense that is activated at the same time. Let pupil remember to think about how different foods feel, what texture they have. Including taste in writing increases awareness of the way time passes within the story.

Benefits of using the Five Senses

The five sense technique can be a part of any method designed to help pupil become strategic, independent writers. Reading a colorful short story or short poem before writing turns on thinking skills and allows pupils to become more interested I the topic. [3] Guiding pupils to visualize as they read gives them confidence; it also helps them learn to think as they write.

Most of us already visualize as we read, but pupil may need encouragement to do so. [4] Talking about visualization and personal memories allow pupil to discover and share what was meaningful to them from the text. Meanwhile the txt has become familiar to them, as their background experience have been activated. Instead of arbitrary list of topics for a descriptive essay, pupils have a connection with a story. That connection offers them something interesting to write about, whether it is driving donkey carts and delivering food or something else.[5]

Reflections on this technique

As a teacher, you can choose any text is particularly vivid and taps into the senses. Write the following steps for visualizing the senses on the board and have pupil copy it. There are five main steps in visualizing the senses, which help to our pupil in writing both an essay and a descriptive story

Let pupil think of a special place they love

1. list things that you see: sightseeing, view of nature
2. list things that you hear: different voices of people, song, sound of rain or wind
3. list things that you feel: touches, warmth and coldness of something
4. list things that you smell: perfume, petrichor
5. list thing that you taste: delicious food, fruit and sweets

CONCLUSION

The technique of five senses is not limited to writing an essay, but can be used in teaching other skills such as reading and listening. In all cases, teachers should use more authentic materials that are useful and relevant for learning English. Moreover, learner's conceptual level and ability to concentrate should be considered. The five senses activities and materials allow pupil of all levels to participate equally in engaging activities and obtain and increased understanding of texts and improved ability to describe and explain their ideas. I consider the technique let pupil to work in appropriate learning corners and experience the freedom in writing tasks that are neither easy nor difficult for their level. From my experience, this is my pupils greatly enjoy.

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